

Prohibition of the International Academy of Architecture.

In consequence of committing tortious acts by members of pseudoscientific International Academy of Architecture, I prohibit it, and expropriate all its assets and property as well all assets and property of its members in accordance with the law of obligation as defined by the German Civil Code (Bürgerliches Gesetzbuch, BGB), provisions of the Constitution of the community Rus', and Berliner Verfassung.

Secondly, I institute criminal proceedings against named organization and its members as well against their supporters and accomplices for aiding and abetting.

Thirdly, I cancel all building works directed or conducted by members of prohibited International Academy of Architecture.

Fourthly, I close all schools organized by and with tortious interference or influence of members of prohibited International Academy of Architecture or their supporters and accomplices.

Fifthly, the continuation of named tortious acts will be prosecuted based on the Nuremberg principles of law.

Dr. Andrej Poleev
Berlin, 16.12.2020.